

ANALYSIS OF MACHINE LEARNING CLASSIFICATION TECHNIQUES FOR IOT ATTACK VECTORS

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Abstract:

Internet of Things (IoT) revolution has challenged IoT security architects to great extent by exploiting the entire layered IoT architecture as attack surface for different cyber-attacks. Rather it has become easier to execute attacks due to non-standardized security architectures of IoT technologies. This study reviews the possibilities of attack surfaces available in IoT ecosystem and techniques used for early detection of malware or attacks. There are a number of attacks in which an IoT device is used as an attack surface for attacking some other system resource including attack vectors such as backdoor, password attacks, cross site scripting, ransomware, DDos, SQL injection, scanning, spying which can infect the IoT system as well as other paired devices through it. This work studies the possible attack types through IoT ecosystem and exploiting machine learning techniques in detection of attacks well in time. A set of machine learning algorithm from each family of machine learning is evaluated for one of the open-source data sets and their performance is compared for seven different IoT device types and eight types of attacks on each of the devices. The performance metrics used for evaluation of algorithms are recall, precision, F-score and accuracy. The study also presents issues related to the variation in performance of machine learning algorithms based on the composition of attributes of different types.

Keywords: IoT Forensic, IoT attacks, IoT attack Classification, ML in IoT malware

1. INTRODUCTION:

Malware can be understood as a software that has malicious effects on the computing environment where it is executed. Malware can infect the system in many ways such as access control, identity theft, data theft, confidentiality breach, privacy and many more. With the increasing use of IoT across variety of applications such as smart home, smart city, Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) health care and personalized gadgets, the attack vectors and surfaces for cyber-attacks have also grown exponentially [1]. One of the primary reasons for increase in vulnerability in IoT infrastructure, is integration of various technologies such as sensors, high speed networks, heterogeneous demographics of IoT devices, without standardization of interfaces [2]. A comprehensive study of present and future IoT infrastructure ecosystems and associated threats and attack vectors have been presented by authors of [3,4] which explains how threats have been propagating through all the layers of IoT architecture and also classifies attacks at each layer. The authors of [5] have classifies attacks prevailing in IoT infrastructure as well as given anatomy of malwares with respect to different layers of IoT architecture as well as proposed security framework for IoT environment which contains preventive, detective, responsive and corrective measures. Of all

types of possible attacks malware has seen taking big share in IoT attack as per [6] as shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: IoT Environment attack scenarios

Increase in usage of IoT has also given attackers a chance to leverage its security loop holes across all the layers of IoT architectures and hence malwares are also increasing their attack surfaces. As per a report [7] the malware industry is growing fast as per fig 2. The usage of IoT in every sector as well as the attacks has guided the IoT security based research in the direction of using other state of the art latest techniques to scan and detect infections at any layer of the ecosystem. Malware analysis using machine learning techniques is therefore also gaining momentum in research community.

Figure 2: Number of malwares year wise

IoT malwares can be analyzed in two ways: static and dynamic. Static malware analysis scans the malware binaries for anomaly without executing them however the dynamic analysis executes the malware binaries to extract their features. IoT ecosystem generates humongous heterogeneous data, which becomes difficult to analyze and hence machine learning techniques can be used to apply AI techniques in detection and hence preventing future attacks if sufficient

past experience data is available [8]. Malware detection techniques have been classified by [9] along with their benefits and limitations in five classes: 1. Signature based 2. Behavior based 3. Heuristic based 4. Anomaly based 5. Statistics based.

Malware classification being one of the primary task in malware detection systems is gaining popularity in research community and different algorithms are getting evaluated for the suitability for data generated by different IoT environments, layers, and devices.

The contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- A. Review of IoT attack surfaces and attack vectors
- B. Review of machine learning techniques used in classification and detection of malwares
- C. Analysis of performance of machine learning algorithms on open-source ToN-IoT dataset which contains datasets with respect to seven IoT devices and eight attack vectors.

Rest of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents literature survey of similar works done in identifying attack surfaces and vectors in IoT ecosystems and classifying malwares using machine learning techniques. Section 3 presents the theoretical techniques used for machine learning, dataset collection and description and the performance metrics used for comparing results. Experimental setup is described in section 4, section 5 discussed the results and section 6 presents conclusion.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

2.1 IoT vulnerability and attacks:

Due to diversity from all perspectives IoT has become inevitable to security threats as the existing security solutions for IT infrastructure are standardized as per corresponding technology standards, however IoT ecosystem has not been able to develop standards. A systematic literature survey was done to understand the IoT attack surfaces, attack vectors and corresponding IoT architecture layer, malware feature extraction using machine learning. Almost 78 Articles from various publishing houses like Springer, Elsevier, IEEE, MDPI etc. ranging in period from 2015 to 2022 are reviewed as per fig 3:

A security landscape for IoT ecosystem has been proposed by[10] along with attack surfaces based on the type of network used and proposed taxonomy of IoT attacks spread across all layers of the architecture. Some researchers in [11] have extracted important features of IoT ecosystem that makes it highly vulnerable to cyber attacks and then classifies threats and challenges accordingly. They have proposed eight features named: interdependency, diversity, constrained, Myriad, unattended, intimacy, mobility and ubiquitous. A smart camera is an important device in IoT ecosystem as it has its presence in almost all IoT applications as smart homes, smart city, IoMT, IIoT etc. therefore a study about vulnerabilities and threats generating out of these is studied and presented in [12].

In [13] the authors have proposed the theory of hybrid threats in IoT ecosystem which are generated due to convergence and interconnection of various elements of an IoT ecosystem, which also comprehends that the threats span all the layers of IoT and needs equal attention. Possibilities of motion-based keystroke attacks through smart wearables is proposed in [14] in which authors have tested feasibility of side channel attacks on mobile phones through the paired smart watches by observing the wrist movements which can be considered as another attack surface and vector for IoT ecosystem. In [15] the authors have classified the IoT vulnerabilities in total nine classes spread over three layered IoT architecture and associated threat with these vulnerabilities. They also proposed IoT vulnerability assessment techniques taxonomy and classified machine learning as one of the important techniques for the same. Studies have also been carried out to propose that hoe Internet of things (IoT) is getting transformed into Internet of Vulnerable Things (IoVT). In their studies in [16] researchers have elaborated how the attack surfaces and vectors are increasing along with the increasing number and types of IoT devices and its applications. They have proposed 10 vulnerabilities across 5 layer architecture along with nine threats and 8 attack surfaces in any IoT ecosystem and demonstrated the threat assessment through 2 case studies of smart Transport and Secured energy management and emphasized that machine learning can be used to assess the probable threats in presented case environments.

2.2 Machine learning models for malware detection:

Machine learning and later on deep learning has gained popularity in recent past as techniques used for IoT malware detection and classification. Malware classification or identification or detection is a task that involves at least two phases: 1. Feature extraction 2. Classification based on extracted features. Feature extraction can be done either from malware binaries directly or from images created from malware binaries. Most of the recent work has used any of these two methods to identify possible attacks at run time in IoT environment.

As a very first work done in the field of using DL techniques for malware detection is [17] which analyzes network interface generated data for binary classification of code a normal or malicious using deep belief network and autoencoder but does not consider data from any other interface in the IoT or IT infrastructure. Classifying malwares using images created form malware binaries was proposed by [18] using Random Forest as machine learning technique to train the model, however this technique requires an additional step of converting binaries to images and then extracting features. Another representative work is presented by [19] which extracts malware features from the malware opcodes which they obtained from Linux based Arm based IoT devices and train them using RNN, however they tested it on very small dataset therefore the possibility of overfitting as the size of date set increases can not be denied. In [20] the researchers performed all three varieties of experiments in IOTPOT dataset i.e. bytes sequence based, Opcodes based and image based malware analysis and comprehend that the performance of opcode based and image based feature generation performs better than byte sequence based, but the testing is done on very small data set and real time conditions are not considered. A review of malware feature extraction techniques, malware classification techniques and malware detection techniques has been done in [21] which proposes that the

performance of classification techniques depends heavily on the distribution of the dataset used and therefore it is possible that the same algorithm performs differently for different data sets. Authors of [22] also use malware images created from malware binaries to classify using CNN XCEPTION model without explicitly extracting any malware features hence saved time, but there logloss was higher than comparative methods. A study was carried out to compare the performance of various machine learning algorithms in IoT malware detection using BoT-IoT data set [23] which used network data carrying 8 protocols and 3 network attack types but did not consider any other type of IoT data. Authors of [24] created a testbed for generation of network data and propagated synthetic binaries of malwares and then used the data set to train the model to malwares using machine learning. A comprehensive study was carried out on classification of IoT data collected at a smart home controller hub using seven popular machine learning, using DS2OS dataset carrying 13 features but need to implement with more features [25]. A modular solution using machine learning is proposed to detect malware after a detailed review of network traffic generated by a testbed environment and manual labeling of IoT malware categories by authors of [26] to make the process of implementation of learning easier however they created synthetic malware database by writing similar scripts as that of original and tested them. In [27] the authors have created a test bed to generate network traffic from a smart home setup and proposed a DNN based IDS system along with a hard coded IDS component. The review of using machine learning techniques in IoT attack / malware classification is tabulated in table1.

Table 1: Review of machine learning techniques used for malware / attack classification in IoT Environment

Reference	Dataset used	Volume of dataset	Technique	Algorithm	Type of dataset	IoT data	Data source type	Malware / Attack categories in dataset	Limiation
[17]	KDDCUP'99	494,021 training data and 311,029 testing	Deep Learning	DBN, Autoencoder	Network	No	Malware Binaries	Five	Analyses only network data
[18]	Malimg, Microsoft	9342	Machine learning	Random forest	Malware dataset	No	Malware binaries	Six	Overhead step of converting malware binary to image
[19]	Linux Debian package repository	281 malware 271 benign	Deep learning	RNN	Arm-64 based IoT Device	Yes	Opcode	-	Very small data set, missing real IoT scenario
[20]	IOT POT	1000 malware and 1000 benign	DL	CNN	Malware binaries	Yes	Opcode, binaries, images	-	
[22]	Malimg, Microsoft	10838 training and 10873 testing dataset	DL	CNN with XCEPTION model	Malware	No	Malware binaries converted to images	9	Conversion of malware binary to malware image
[23]	BoT-IoT		ML	AdaBoost, NB, KNN, QDA, MLP3, IDA	Network dataset	Yes	BoT-IoT	3	Only supervised algorithms tested
[24]	Private honeypot data	133 bashlite and 123 Mirai	ML	NB, KNN, RF	Malware	No	Malware images	2	Not all IoT scenarios considered
[25]	DS2OS	357952	ML	LR,SVM,DT,RF, ANN	Network , OS, IoT devices	yes	Feature set	7	Comparative study of existing algorithms, No new algorithm
[26]	Privately created thru testbed		ML	RF, KNN, GNB	Network	No	Synthetically generated malware binaries	4	Comparison of existing algorithms
[27]		59529 total	DL	DNN	Network	Yes	Network data	15	Only network data is classified
[28]	BoT-IoT		DL	CNN	Network	No	Network data		Only network data is classified

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS:

The study carried out in this paper represents performance evaluation of various machine learning algorithms on the datasets obtained from various IoT and IIoT setup. The overall methodology is presented in fig 3. We have used opensource data set ToN-IoT dataset for model building and evaluation of the model. The ToN_IoT datasets are new generations of Industry 4.0/Internet of Things (IoT) and Industrial IoT (IIoT) datasets for evaluating the fidelity and efficiency of different cybersecurity applications based on Artificial Intelligence (AI), i.e., Machine/Deep Learning algorithms [28].

Figure 3: Proposed process flow for evaluation of malware attack detection in IoT Environment using machine learning models

The IoT data has lot of heterogeneity that makes uniform analysis of any technique to process data becomes difficult which increases the complexity while doing forensic analysis of the IoT ecosystem generated data[29]. ToN-IoT Data also has a collection of seven types of IoT device data: Iot_Fridge, IoT_GPS_Tracker, IoT_motion_light, IoT_thermostat, IoT_garage_door, IoT_modbus each of which are having different features set extracted from telemetry data sets of IoT and IIoT sensors. The data set has collectively 3799375 entries in total categorizes as per fig 4.

Figure 4: ToN-IoT data distribution based on attack vectors

4. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND:

4.1 Data Description:

The Ton-IoT data set is further divided into 4 subsets containing: data collected from IoT devices using telemetry, data sets for Linux and window's OS and Network data sets. This study uses IoT devices data sets as the idea is to understand the prerequisites of implementing an IDS at IoT device level. The test bed used by [29] has generated telemetry data from IoT devices which is then converted to the featured data in CSV format. As per the proposed methodology first the data set was collected and was analyzed thoroughly for the composition of anomaly based and normal data as presented in table 1. This shows that Back door is the most probable attack on IoT devices grabbing almost 50% of the total attacks in the given scenario of IoT and IIoT setup.

Table 2: Device wise and attack wise data volume metric of the ToN-IoT dataset

Attack vector	Backdoor	Ddos	Injection	Normal	password	Ransomware	Scanning	XSS	Total
Fridge	35568	10233	7079	500827	28425	2042	2902	2042	589118
GPS Tracker	35571	10226	6904	513849	25176	2833	550	577	595686
Motion Light	28209	8121	5595	388328	17521	2264	1775	449	452262
Weather	35641	15182	9726	559718	25715	2865	529	866	650242
Garage door	35568	10230	6331	515443	19287	2902	529	1156	591446
ModBus	40035	0	7079	405904	24269	0	529	577	478393
Thermostat	35568	0	9498	385953	8435	2264	61	449	442228
Total data attack wise	246160	53992	52212	3270022	148828	15170	6875	6116	3799375
% w.r.t total data	6.47896	1.421076	1.374226	86.06737	3.917171	0.399276	0.180951	0.160974	
% w.r.t. malicious data	46.50205	10.19962	9.863361	--	28.11508	2.865763	1.298755	1.155373	

Feature sets extracted by [28] while creating ToN-IoT are as follows in Figure 5 (a-g): (f)

Service profile: IoT Fridge activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	fridge_temperature	Number	Temperature measurement of a fridge sensor linked to the network
4	temp_condition	String	Temperature conditions of a fridge sensor linked to the network, where temperature is high or low based on a predefined threshold value
5	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
6	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(a)

Service profile: IoT Garage_Door activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	door_state	Boolean	State of a door sensor linked to the network where the door is closed or open
4	sphone_signal	Boolean	State of receiving the door signal on a phone where the signal is true or false
5	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
6	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(b)

Service profile: IoT GPS_Tracker activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	latitude	Number	Latitude value of GPS tracker sensor linked to the network
4	longitude	Number	Longitude value of GPS tracker sensor linked to the network
5	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
6	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(c)

Service profile: IoT Modbus activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
2	FC1_Read_Input_Register	Number	Modbus function code that is responsible for reading an input register
3	FC2_Read_Discrete_Value	Number	Modbus function code that is in charge of reading a discrete value
4	FC3_Read_Holding_Register	Number	Modbus function code that is responsible for reading a holding register
5	FC4_Read_Coil	Number	Modbus function code that is responsible for reading a coil
6	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
7	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(d)

Service profile: IoT Motion_Light activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	motion_status	Number	Status of a motion sensor is either on (i.e., 1) or off (i.e., 0)
4	light_status	Boolean	Status of a light sensor is either on or off
5	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
6	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(e)

Service profile: IoT Thermostat activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	current_temperature	Number	Current temperature reading of a thermostat sensor connected with the network
4	thermostat_status	Boolean	Status of a thermostat sensor is either on or off
5	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
6	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(f)

Service profile: IoT Weather activity			
ID	Feature	Type	Description
1	date	Date	Date of logging IoT telemetry data
2	time	Time	Time of logging IoT telemetry data
3	temperature	Number	Temperature measurements of a weather sensor linked to the network
4	pressure	Number	Pressure readings of a weather sensor linked to the network
5	humidity	Number	Humidity readings of a weather sensor linked to the network
6	label	Number	Tag normal and attack records, where 0 indicates normal and 1 indicates attacks
7	type	String	Tag attack categories, such as normal, DoS, DDoS and backdoor attacks, and normal records

(g)

Figure 5 : Feature Description ToN-IoT dataset : (a) IoT_Fridge (b) IoT_Garage_door (c) IoT_GPS_Tracker (d) IoT_Modbus (e) IoT_Motion_light_activity (f) IoT_Thermostate_Activity (g) IoT_Weather_activity

For any data set of being suitable to supply to any machine learning technique it needs to be prepared as per the suitability. At first hand the data needs to be checked for missing values and then transformed into numeric or nominal values as classifiers work on these attributes only. IoT_garage_door data subset needed to transformed the string values “true” and “false” to ‘T’ and ‘F’ nominal values respectively. All the seven data subsets are too bulky and take lot of time to build model using all entries of instances, therefore the datasets were resampled using Weka.

4.2 Theoretical details of machine learning models:

4.2.1 J48 Decision tree: This algorithm belongs to the class of decision tree technique and is an improvised version of ID3 algorithm. It uses a divide and conquers approach to growing decision trees and works in 2 phases: construction and Computing information gain. Construction of the trees is done by similarity of cases to the class

A. Construction: Some basic steps are given below to construct tree: • First, check whether all cases belongs to same class, then the tree is a leaf and is labelled with that class. • For each attribute, calculate the information and information gain. • Find the best splitting attribute (depending upon current selection criterion)

B. Computing information gain for J48“Entropy” is used in this process. Entropy is a measure of disorder of data. Entropy is measured in bits, nats or bans. This is also called measurement of uncertainty in any random variable. Just suppose that there is a fair coin, if single toss is performed on that coin than its entropy will be one bit [30]

4.2.2 Random Forest: As obvious from the name a random forest, a supervised, high speed classification algorithm, can be considered as a collection of predefined binary decision trees. Many decision trees when build together form a random forest, and it evaluates the model by averaging the predictions of each participating tree. It usually has much better predictive accuracy than a single decision tree. In general, the more trees in the forest the more robust the forest looks. In this study Random tree as well as random forest is analysed against evaluation parameters.[31]

4.2.3 Nearest Neighbour: K- Nearest neighbour can be considered as a classification technique which considers K number of nearest neighbour before classifying an item. Since the training examples are needed at runtime, i.e., they need to be in memory at runtime, it is sometimes also called Memory-based Classification. Because induction is delayed to runtime, it is considered a Lazy Learning technique. Because classification is based directly on the training examples, it is also called Example-based Classification, or Case-based Classification [32]. In our study we have considered the variation Kstar.

4.3 Evaluation metrics:

This study evaluates various machine learning techniques as mentioned in previous section, for classification of IoT data, by measuring the following performance parameters: Confusion matrix, recall, precision, and F1 score and accuracy. Evaluation of Precision (P) and recall (R) is important when the data set has an imbalanced classification. Precision can be understood as

the parameter that measures the goodness of the model in classifying positive classes. Precision can be defined as the ratio of the number of true positives divided by the sum of the true positives and false positives.

$$\text{Precision} = \text{True Positives} / (\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}) \quad (1)$$

Recall is calculated as the ratio of the number of true positives divided by the sum of the true positives and the false negatives.

$$\text{Recall (TPR)} = \text{True Positives} / (\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negative}) \quad (2)$$

F1 score is the weighted harmonic mean of the precision and recall and reflects the balance between P and R.

$$F1 = 2 *(\text{precision} _ \text{recall}) / (\text{precision} + \text{recall}) \quad (3)$$

5. RESULT ANALYSIS:

5.1 Experimental setup:

The experiment was done using Device name DESKTOP-604T74P, Processor AMD Ryzen 5 2500U with Radeon Vega Mobile Gfx, 2.00 GHz, Installed RAM 20.0 GB (17.9 GB usable), 64-bit operating system, x64-based proc, with Windows 10 version 21H2 Windows Feature Experience Pack 120.2212.4180.0. An open-source machine language implementation workbench Weka 3.9.6 is used to exploit data sets with various machine learning algorithms and evaluate their performance for ToN-IoT dataset available in seven categories of IoT devices. The datasets were subjected to total 5 algorithms namely J48(Decision Tree), Random Tree, Random Forest, IBk and Kstar. with the cross-validation method using 5 folds. The experiment was repeated for all seven IoT devices datasets and their performance metrics were recorded in table 2.

Table 3: Performance analysis of Ton- IoT dataset for Random Forest, K-Star and J48 algorithms												
Performance metrics												
S.No.	IoT_Device		Random Forest			Lazy Kstar			J48			
		Attack Vector	Recall	Precision	F-Score	Recall	Precision	F-Score	Recall	Precision	F-Score	
1	Refridgerator	Backdoor	0.991	0.925	0.957	1	1	1	0.99	1	0.99	
		Ddos	0.996	0.997	0.996	1	1	1	0.999	0.999	0.999	
		Injection	0.997	0.995	0.996	1	1	1	1	0.99	0.99	
		Normal	0.968	1	0.984	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password				1	1	1	0.99	1	1	
		Ransomware	0.973	0.705	0.818	1	1	1	1	0.998	0.999	
		Scanning	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
		XSS	0.95	0.95	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	
2	GPS Tracker	Backdoor	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.999	1	1	
		Ddos	0.989	0.978	0.983	1	1	1	0.999	1	0.999	
		Injection	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0.999	0.999	
		Normal	0.998	1	0.999	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	0.987	0.987	0.987	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ransomware	0.987	0.979	0.983	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Scanning	1	0.978	0.989	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		XSS	0.944	0.951	0.947	1	1	1	1	1	1	
3	Motion Light	Backdoor	0.985	0.992	0.989	1	1	1	0.99	0.99	0.99	
		Ddos	0.983	0.757	0.855	1	1	1	0.99	1	1	
		Injection	1	0.848	0.918	1	1	1	1	0.99	1	
		Normal	0.894	0.999	0.944	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	0.806	0.81	0.808	0.832	0.954	0.889	0.8	0.99	0.88	
		Ransomware	0.993	0.658	0.792	0.753	0.422	0.541	1	0.98	0.99	
		Scanning	0.857	0.142	0.243	1	1	1	0.966	0.251	0.398	
		XSS	0.969	0.855	0.908	1	1	1	1	1	1	
4	Weather	Backdoor	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.998	0.996	0.997	1	1	1	
		Ddos	1	0.974	0.987	0.999	0.999	0.999	1	1	1	
		Injection	1	1	1	0.996	0.998	0.997	1	1	1	
		Normal	0.984	1	0.992	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	0.998	0.998	0.998	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ransomware	1	0.851	0.919	0.998	0.999	0.998	1	0.999	1	
		Scanning	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		XSS	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
5	Garrage door	Backdoor	0.984	0.986	0.985	1	1	1	1	0.996	0.998	
		Ddos	0.988	0.987	0.988	1	1	1	0.999	1	0.999	
		Injection	0.998	0.998	0.998	1	1	1	1	0.998	0.999	
		Normal	0.963	1	0.981	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ransomware	0.963	0.496	0.654	1	1	1	0.995	1	0.997	
		Scanning	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		XSS	0.944	0.956	0.95	1	1	1	1	1	1	
6	ModBus	Backdoor	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ddos	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Injection	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Normal	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	1	1	1	1	0.999	0.999	1	0.999	0.999	
		Ransomware	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Scanning	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		XSS	1	1	1	0.991	1	0.995	0.991	1	0.995	
7	Thermostat	Backdoor	0.997	0.984	0.99	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ddos	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Injection	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Normal	0.979	1	0.989	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		password	0.995	0.993	0.994	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		Ransomware	0.991	0.699	0.819	1	1	1	1	0.998	0.999	
		Scanning	NA	NA	NA	1	1	1	1	1	1	
		XSS	0.988	0.963	0.975	1	1	1	1	1	1	

True positive (TP) False positive (FP) are recorded for each data set and thus Recall and precision is computed. On reviewing the results, it can be observed that in IoT environment the data collected from the devices is of diverse type and has diverse composition of numerical and

nominal values, therefore no single machine learning algorithm can be considered best because of such nature of data set. If average performance of these algorithms over all data sets is compared Lazy K-star appears to perform best with average Precision 0.974, recall 0.970 and f-score 0.971 in general for the variety of data sets considered in the experiment. Another observation is that Random Forest performs worst with parameters precision 0.928, recall 0.8798 and f-score 0.895.

6. CONCLUSION:

The experiment done in this study has executed three different machine learning algorithms on the ToN-IoT datasets collected from IoT devices and it is noticed that none of the algorithms can be considered best on the basis of comparative analysis. Also, the memory requirement of the algorithms is beyond the local memory of the devices and hence some lightweight algorithms must be devised to be used at the devices for detection of malwares or malicious activity. This study can be further extended to federated IoT environment to test the performance of various machine learning algorithms. Also this study includes running existing algorithms only and can be extended to implement the same algorithms with improvements for IoT environment.

7. STATEMENT OF DISCLOSURE:

The authors declare that there is no conflict of competing interest for any financial or non-financial of application of this research work.

8. DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT:

The study has used publicly available ToN-IoT dataset which can be found at: <https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/toniot-datasets>

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